

The Common Impact Data Standard

An Ontology for Representing Impact

Version 2.1, May 2023

Ontology URL: http://ontology.commonapproach.org/owl/cids_v2.1.owl

Namespace: <http://ontology.commonapproach.org/>

Suggested Prefix: cids

For further information, contact: info@commonapproach.org

Recommended Attribution:

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<https://www.commonapproach.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Common-Impact-Data-Standard-V2.1.pdf>

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